

REFLECTIVE CONVERSATIONS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF ANALYTICAL SKILLS OF GRADE 8 STUDENTS IN WORLD HISTORY

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ABSTRACT

This research was conducted to identify the impact of reflective conversations in terms of descriptive reflection, perceptive reflection, receptive reflection, interactive reflection, and critical reflection in the development of analytical skills such as communicating, creative thinking, critical thinking, data analyzing, and researching in World History. Using a descriptive-experimental method of research, it involved the 40 purposively selected Grade 8 students of Talipan National High School, during the school year 2020-2021. The students were given a self-made pre-test, then they were engaged in reflective conversations, afterwards, a post-test was given followed by a questionnaire on their perception on reflective conversations. Pearson product-moment correlation, T-Test, Mean and Standard Deviation were used to analyze and interpret the data. The results revealed that the students agree that reflective conversations in terms of descriptive, perceptive, receptive, interactive, and critical reflection helped them in developing their analytical skills. There is improvement on the students post analytical skills wherein the pre-test resulted with Fairly Satisfactory on communicating, critical thinking, data analyzing, and researching, and Did not Meet expectations on creative thinking. While the post-test resulted with Very Satisfactory on communicating, and data analyzing, Satisfactory on critical thinking, and researching, and Did not Meet Expectation on creative thinking. Based on the findings, the following conclusions were derived: there is a significant difference on the pre-test and post-test mean scores performance of the students on analytical skills assessment. Moreover, there is a significant relationship between the students' perception on reflective conversations in terms of descriptive, perceptive, receptive, and interactive reflection, and their post-analytical skills in terms of communicating, creative thinking, critical thinking, and data analyzing while there is no significant relationship between critical reflection and all post-analytical skills.

Keywords: World History, reflective conversations, analytical skills, descriptive - experimental research, Philippines